

FEASIBILITY STUDY OF A CFRP BOSS FOR APPLICATION IN LINERLESS COMPOSITE TYPE V TANKS

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CFRP TANK

BOSS

CFRP VS. METALL BOSS

- Less structural weight
- Reduced CTE mismatch → reduced thermal stresses in dome/boss-interface
- Enhanced bonding behavior in dome/boss-interface
- Reduced heat entry in tank system

PREFORM

- Load path conform layup

MATRIX SYSTEM

- Highly toughened epoxy matrix for cryogenic application
- Enhanced micro-crack resistance

INSERTS

- In-Situ application during preforming
- High tear-out force

PROCESS

- Vacuum infusion process
- RTM process in next step for less voids

SPIRAL WEAVE FABRIC

- Fibers oriented in
 - 0° radial
 - 90° circumferential

2K TOUGHENED LIQUID INFUSION SYSTEM

- $K_{IC} = 0,97 \pm 0,18 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$
- $G_{IC} 360 \text{ J/m}^2$

→ Fracture energy release maximized for enabling interlaminar toughening mechanisms

C-Fiber in Epoxy

Crack Plastic Zone

Plastic Zone: $R_p = 2-3 \mu\text{m}$

TEAR-OUT TESTING

INSERT TEAR-OUT

FORCE [kN]

DISPLACEMENT [mm]

$F_{max} = 18.2 \text{ kN}$

$F_{Op} = 7.5 \text{ kN}$

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